

Factors Associated with Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) Program in Maa District

Liezel A. Villahermosa

Abstract. The study aimed to determine the extent of factors associated with water, sanitation, and hygiene and the extent of WASH program of public elementary schools in Maa District. This study employed a non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing descriptive-correlation method. Validated questionnaire and Universal sampling procedure were utilized considering the minimal number of teachers in the research locale. One hundred twenty (120) public elementary school teachers were the respondents of the study. Using mean, pearson-r, and regression analysis, the findings revealed that the factors associated with water, sanitation, and hygiene was very extensive while the extent of WASH program of public elementary schools was also very extensive. Moreover, the overall results disclosed that indicators for the water, sanitation, and hygiene were positively correlated to the WASH program of public elementary schools. Further, results from the regression analysis revealed the following have a strong influence of water, sanitation, and hygiene on the WASH program of public elementary schools: prevention and control practices, sanitation and hygiene and evaluation and consultation. It is recommended that the DepEd should allocate sufficient resources and implement stronger policies to sustain and expand the WASH program, particularly in underserved schools, ensuring equitable access to clean water and sanitation facilities. It is also recommended that the teachers should integrate WASH education into daily classroom routines and activities to reinforce hygiene awareness and encourage lifelong healthy habits among learners.

KEY WORDS

1. water 2. sanitation and hygiene, 3. wash program

Date Received: December 18, 2025 — Date Reviewed: January 4, 2026 — Date Published: February 14, 2026

1. Introduction

Hygiene and sanitation are the two most important things pertaining to good health. Sufficient water, toilets, and hand-washing amenities are required for good hygiene and sanitation, while its shortage may pose many health problems to people. Water, hygiene, and sanitation problems have led several children in the developing world to become sick and fall prey to infections and diarrheal disease. It is expected that in a study on the factors associated with WASH programs in public elementary schools, the learners would gain in terms of health, reduced absenteeism, and an improved learning environment. For teachers and school staff, a better and safer workplace would be ensured. The school heads and administrators would be

guided in decision-making and resource allocation. For parents, the benefit is indirect in the form of healthier children. The DOST could also use the findings in further improving existing policies and programs, and LGUs and health officers align initiatives to school needs. NGOs and development partners could determine what areas of intervention they can provide support in, and future researchers can use this study in further academic discourse. The factors of WASH programming in public elementary schools were selected because they have major roles to play in the successful implementation and sustainability of hygiene and sanitation initiatives. These stakeholders include learners, teachers, school heads, parents, DepEd officials, LGUs, and health workers who will have vested interests in or be directly impacted by the programs' success. Knowledge of this involvement facilitates a greater understanding of 2 disparities in strengths, gaps, and points of intervention that best ensure healthy WASH practices to promote health and safety toward quality education in schools. In the global view, the study of school heads' motivational techniques and teachers' personal competencies in the public elementary schools has shown that effective leadership is very crucial in bringing about improvement in teacher performance. Other recent research has pointed out that transformational leadership which entails inspirational motivation, individualized consideration, and intellectual stimulation has drastically influenced teachers' motivation and competencies. For example, Rachmad et al., (2023) establish that transformational leadership and teacher motivation jointly account for 77.6 percent of the variation in teacher performance, meaning leadership styles have severe impacts on educational outcomes. Recent global studies have emphasized the different actors with regard to their respective roles in the implementation of WASH in public elementary schools. In Zambia, Winter et al., 2021 examine how school-based WASH programs fa-

cilitated by organizations such as World Vision enabled children to act as change agents and spread community and household engagement on improved hygiene practices. Their study discussed the engagement of learners, teachers, and caregivers in the facilitation of sustainability in hygiene practices. In the study of Bansuan (2023), evaluated the comprehensive WASH program in South Central Mindanao, emphasizing the importance of coordinated efforts among school administrators, local government units, and non-governmental organizations in enhancing program outcomes. These studies 3 underscore that the collaborative involvement of diverse stakeholders is crucial for the sustainability and effectiveness of WASH initiatives in public elementary schools. Similarly, in the Philippines, a cluster-randomized controlled trial by Poague et al., (2022) demonstrated that comprehensive WASH interventions in Metro Manila schools significantly improved students' health literacy, reduced malnutrition, and enhanced handwashing behaviors. The study emphasized the collaborative efforts of school staff, parents, and local authorities in achieving these outcomes. Sangalang et al., (2022) conducted a cluster-randomized controlled trial in Metro Manila schools, demonstrating that comprehensive WASH interventions significantly improved learners' health literacy, reduced malnutrition, and enhanced handwashing behaviors. The study emphasized the collaborative efforts of school staff, parents, and local authorities in achieving these outcomes. Moreover, Dalisay et al., (2024) conducted a qualitative analysis using the One Health lens, revealing that effective WASH implementation is bolstered by public-private partnerships, community engagement, and recognition of innovative practices within schools. In the context of Maa District, several pressing challenges affect the effective implementation of the Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) program in public elementary schools. One key issue is the inconsistent

access to clean and safe water, which hampers daily hygiene practices such as handwashing and drinking water provision. Many schools rely on unreliable water sources, especially during dry seasons, affecting both learners and staff. Sanitation facilities are often inadequate, with some toilets either non-functional, lacking privacy, or shared by too many users, which compromises learners' comfort and safety particularly that of young girls. Poor maintenance of these facilities further aggravates the problem, as limited manpower and financial resources make regular cleaning and repairs difficult. Hygiene education is not always integrated into the daily school routine, resulting in learner lacking proper knowledge and habits for personal hygiene. Teachers and school heads are often overextended with multiple responsibilities, making it difficult to monitor and promote WASH practices consistently. Budget constraints at both school and barangay levels contribute to delays in infrastructure improvements and hygiene campaigns. The coordination between the Department of Education, local health offices, and community stakeholders is sometimes weak, leading to fragmented or short-term WASH efforts. These local problems highlight the need for a more sustainable, well-supported, and community-based approach to strengthening the WASH program in Maa District. The researcher conducted the study on the WASH (Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene) program to assess the current conditions and identify the specific challenges faced by public elementary schools in Maa District. This is intended to provide evidence-based insights that can help improve hygiene practices, sanitation infrastructure, and access to clean water for students and staff. By understanding the factors affecting the effectiveness of the WASH program, the study aims to support local policy development and promote a healthier, safer learning environment for school communities.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study —This study on the factors associated with Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) Program in Maa District is anchored on three interrelated theories: the Health Belief Model (HBM) by Rosenstock (1974), the Social Ecological Model (SEM) by McLeroy et al., (1988), and the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) by Ajzen (1991). These theories are used to explain the various personal, social, environmental, and behavioral factors that influence the implementation and sustainability of WASH practices in schools. The framework is also guided by DepEd Order No. 10, s. 2016, which institutionalizes the WASH in Schools Program and sets the national policy on improving water access, sanitation facilities, and hygiene education in all public schools. The Health Belief Model (HBM) emphasizes that individuals are more likely to engage in health-related behaviors if they believe they are susceptible to a health problem, believe it could have serious consequences, and believe that taking action would reduce the risk. In the context of the WASH program in Maa District, this theory is vital in understanding how learners, teachers, and parents perceive the risks of poor hygiene and sanitation, such as the spread of diarrheal diseases or infections. When stakeholders are aware of these risks and understand the benefits of preventive actions like handwashing, using clean toilets, and drinking safe water they are more likely to support and follow WASH practices. The Social Ecological Model (SEM) provides a broader perspective by considering the multiple levels that influence behavior: individual, interpersonal, institutional, community, and policy. Applying SEM to this study highlights the importance of supportive school leadership, teacher modeling, parental involvement, and local government engagement in ensuring that WASH practices are consistently observed. In schools across Maa District, the availability of WASH infrastructure, regular hygiene promo-

sidered worth conducting to explore naturally occurring conditions and ascertain the level of association among variables in the real world. Bansuan (2023) also validated this methodology by noting its applicability in defining individual or group attributes and delineating the nature of available data based on empirical observation. Here, the research was descriptive in that it sought to evaluate the factors correlated with the adoption of WINS (Wash in Schools) practices and the Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) program in the public elementary schools in Maa District, Division of Davao City. It was correlational in that it aimed to identify whether and how these factors were correlated with the quality and extent of WASH implementation in schools. By employing this study design, the research yielded insightful findings regarding the impact of school-level factors such as infrastructure, administrative support, and stakeholder participation on the achievement or constraint of WINS and WASH programs, thus informing evidence-based school hygiene and sanitation program improvement.

2.2. Ethical Consideration—The study rigidly followed the laid-out protocols and standard guidelines in the conduct of the research, especially in the ethical handling of the population data. Under the observation of study protocol evaluation standards, all procedures were executed with transparency, confidentiality, and respect for participants' rights. A survey questionnaire backed by pertinent literature and quotes from renowned authors was presented for in-depth review and appraisal. Once formal approval was obtained from the Ethics Committee, the researcher moved on to the next stage of the research, with all ethical issues being consistently maintained.

2.3. Research Respondents—The target respondents for this study were married intermediate public elementary school teachers in Maa District who handled grades 4 to 6 and had teaching experience under the Department of

Education (DepEd). To determine the appropriate sample size from this population, Slovin's formula ($n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$) was applied, where N represented the total population size and e was the margin of error. Assuming a total population (N) of 120 intermediate teachers in Maa District (based on available data) and using a standard 5% margin of error ($e = 0.05$), the calculation yielded a sample size of approximately 92 teachers. This computation ensured that the study maintained a 95% confidence level while accounting for practical constraints in surveying the entire population. The derived sample size of 92 respondents provided a statistically representative subset to analyze stress-related conflicts and coping mechanisms among these teachers.

2.4. Research Instrument—This study adapted the questionnaire on the Three Star Approach by UNICEF GIZ (2013). This theory highlighted the stepwise recognition system developed by UNICEF and GIZ to support schools in progressively achieving national WASH standards. It encouraged schools to make incremental improvements in WASH services, starting from basic practices and moving towards comprehensive, sustainable solutions. This was supported by DepEd Order No. 10, s. 2016, which outlined the policy and guidelines for comprehensive WASH implementation. The TSA provided a clear framework for schools to assess their current WASH status, plan improvements, and receive recognition for their efforts, thereby motivating continuous progress and stakeholder engagement. The questionnaire was adopted mainly according to the researcher's preferences to suit the needs of the study. The adapted questionnaire was validated by experts from the DepEd-Division of Davao City. The validity of the instrument was ensured through expert opinions and pilot testing. To ensure the reliability of the instrument, a pilot test was conducted, and the value of Cronbach's Alpha was calculated at 0.893. The questionnaire was divided into two

sections: factors associated with WASH practices and the Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene program of public elementary schools. Hence, the Cronbach's value of the construct met the minimum reliability of 0.893, which meant that the measures used were consistent enough for the study. In terms of the instrument's face validity, the items were modified to suit the purpose

of this study and were validated by experts. The questionnaire was presented to the adviser for comments, corrections, and suggestions. Part 1 of the questionnaire contained the items factors associated with WASH with the following: prevention and control practices, sanitation and hygiene and evaluation and consultation.

Scale Descriptive Ratings and Interpretation of Factors Associated with WASH

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20–5.00	Very Extensive	Factors associated with WASH are always evident.
3.40–4.19	Extensive	Factors associated with WASH are oftentimes evident.
2.60–3.39	Moderately Extensive	Factors associated with WASH are sometimes evident.
1.80–2.59	Less Extensive	Factors associated with WASH are rarely evident.
1.00–1.79	Not Extensive	Factors associated with WASH are not evident.

Scale Descriptive Ratings and Interpretation of Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) Programs

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20–5.00	Very Extensive	Water sanitation and hygiene programs are always evident.
3.40–4.19	Extensive	Water sanitation and hygiene programs are oftentimes evident.
2.60–3.39	Moderately Extensive	Water sanitation and hygiene programs are sometimes evident.
1.80–2.59	Less Extensive	Water sanitation and hygiene programs are rarely evident.
1.00–1.79	Not Extensive	Water sanitation and hygiene programs are not evident.

2.5. *Data Gathering Procedure*—Permission to conduct study. The first step in the data-gathering procedure was to secure permission to conduct the study from the appropriate authorities. The researcher formally obtained approval through the proper channels. On August 4, 2025, the researcher's study was examined and evaluated by the RMC Research Ethics Committee as part of the initial review process. An endorsement was subsequently secured from the Dean of the RMC Graduate School on August 9, 2025, signifying institutional support for

the research. Thereafter, the Schools Division Superintendent granted approval for the conduct of the study on September 5, 2025. Finally, the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS) of Maa approved the distribution of survey questionnaires to the identified schools, allowing the researcher to proceed with data collection in accordance with established protocols and ethical standards. Distribution and retrieval of questionnaires. On September 16, 2025, the researcher distributed the questionnaires to the selected respondents through printed copies. Clear and

simple instructions were provided to guide the respondents in accurately completing the forms. Once completed, the questionnaires were collected by the researcher through secure online submission or coordinated retrieval of printed copies. Throughout the entire process, strict measures were followed to maintain the confidentiality of responses and to ensure the accuracy and integrity of the collected data. Collection and statistical treatment of data. The researcher personally retrieved the questionnaires on October 13, 2025, ensuring that all responses were collected in an organized and secure manner. The collected questionnaires were then submitted to the designated statistician for thorough analysis. The researcher and the statistician worked closely to meticulously tabulate the collected data, ensuring that all responses were accurately organized for analysis. Each piece

of information was carefully reviewed to maintain consistency and completeness, providing a solid foundation for the subsequent statistical procedures. After tabulation, they conducted a comprehensive analysis of the data, applying rigorous statistical methods to examine patterns, relationships, and significant findings. These steps ensured the accuracy and reliability of the results, allowing the study to produce valid and meaningful conclusions. The researcher, in collaboration with the statistician, oversaw the encoding, tabulation, and application of appropriate statistical treatments to analyze the results with accuracy and integrity. These analyses were guided by the study's research objectives and methodological framework to ensure that findings were valid, reliable, and aligned with the goals of evaluating the implementation of the WASH program.

2.6. Data Analysis—The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study: Mean It was used to determine the extent of factors associated with WASH in public elementary schools in Maa District, Division of Davao City. The mean was chosen as the primary statistical tool in analyzing the factors associated with the WASH (Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene) program in public elementary schools in Maa District because it effectively summarized the central tendency of responses across different variables. Since the study utilized survey data collected through Likert-scale questionnaires, the mean provided a clear and straightforward measure of the average perception or level of agreement among the respondents regarding specific aspects of the WASH program, such as water availability, sanitation facilities, hygiene practices, and administrative support. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson-r) This statistical tool was used to determine the significant components of factors associated

with Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) in public elementary schools in Maa District, Division of Davao City. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson-r) was chosen as the statistical tool in this study to determine the strength and direction of the relationship between the identified factors and the implementation of the WASH (Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene) program in public elementary schools in Maa District. Since the study aimed to examine whether variables such as school facilities, administrative support, hygiene education, and teacher involvement were significantly associated with the effectiveness of the WASH program, Pearson-r was appropriate for measuring the degree of linear correlation between these continuous variables. Multiple Linear Regression This was utilized to determine the significance of factors associated with WASH practices influencing water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) in public elementary schools of Maa District, Division of Davao City. Multiple Linear Regression was

selected as the statistical tool in this study to determine how multiple independent variables collectively influenced the implementation of the WASH (Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene) program in public elementary schools in Maa District. This method was appropriate because the study sought to examine the combined effects of various factors such as water accessibility, sanitation infrastructure, hygiene education, administrative support, and teacher involvement on the overall effectiveness of the WASH program.

3. Results and Discussion

Presented in this chapter are the results of the data gathered. Two sets of research were employed to determine the extent of factors associated with water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) and water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) program of performance of public elementary schools in Maa District, Division of Davao City. The discussion of results and interpretations was systematically organized in alignment with the study's statement of the problems to ensure coherence and clarity. Each finding was analyzed and interpreted based on the corresponding research questions, allowing for a logical flow of discussion. This structure facilitated a comprehensive understanding of how each variable contributes to the overall assessment of the Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) initiatives in public elementary schools. The presentation of interpretations was arranged according to major subheadings, beginning with the extent of factors associated with WASH in terms of prevention and control practices, sanitation and hygiene, and evaluation and consultation. It was followed by the assessment of the extent of WASH programs in public elementary schools within the Maa District, Division of Davao City, focusing on the availability of water facilities, handwashing facilities, and toilet facilities. Finally, the discussion identified which domains of WASH-related factors significantly influenced the overall effectiveness of WASH programs, providing a clear basis for understanding the strengths and areas for improvement in school-based WASH implementation.

3.1. Extent of Factors Associated with Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH)—Water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) are critical factors that directly influence public health, environmental sustainability, and socio-economic development. Access to clean water ensures hydration and reduces the risk of waterborne diseases, while proper sanitation systems prevent contamination and the spread of pathogens. Hygiene practices, such as handwashing with soap, play a vital role in breaking the transmission cycle of infectious illnesses. These elements are interconnected, as inadequate water supply can hinder sanitation and hygiene efforts, leading to increased vulnerability to diseases and poor quality of life. Summary on the Extent of Factors Associated with Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene Table 1 depicted on the summary extent of factors associated with water, sanitation, and hygiene with overall mean score of 4.21, interpreted as Very Extensive, indicates that the implementation of WASH-related practices in schools is highly evident and well-integrated into school routines. This suggests that teachers and school staff are actively promoting hygiene awareness, maintaining sanitation facilities, and conducting evaluation and consultation efforts to ensure the sustainability of WASH programs. According to Quinan (2025), continuous assessment and stakeholder engagement are vital for sustaining the gains of WASH initiatives, as they enhance accountability and community participation in school health programs.

Table 1. Summary on the Extent of Factors Associated with Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH)

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Prevention and Control Practices	4.19	Extensive
2	Sanitation and Hygiene	4.22	Very Extensive
3	Evaluation and Consultation	4.23	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.21	Very Extensive

In order to ensure the successful implementation and monitoring of WASH activities, schools are proactive in conducting regular evaluations and consultations with stakeholders, including students, parents, and community members, as indicated by the highest mean of 4.23 for Evaluation and Consultation (Very Extensive). This result is consistent with Tadesse et al., (2024), who highlighted that collaborative consultation and participatory evaluation greatly enhance WASH outcomes in basic education institutions. On the other hand, schools do a good job of implementing preventive health measures, but there is still room for improvement in infection control, health monitoring, and the regular supply of hygiene materials, as indicated by the lowest mean of 4.19 for Prevention and Control Practices (Extensive). While schools often uphold preventive norms, Kumar et al., (2024) pointed out that infrastructure investment and recurring reinforcement of hygiene education are crucial for maintaining surroundings that are safe for people’s health. The outcome is in line with the opinion of Pereira et al., (2024), who recently confirmed with strong evidence that successful school WASH programs rely on an integrated approach that includes regular evaluation and stakeholder consultation to maintain behavior change and guarantee facility functionality, consistent prevention and control practices like handwashing with soap, and adequate sanitation and hygiene infrastructure.

3.2. *Extent of Water, Sanitation, Hygiene (WASH) Program*—The Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) Program is a global initiative aimed at improving health and well-being by ensuring access to safe water, adequate sanitation, and proper hygiene practices. WASH addresses critical public health challenges by reducing the spread of waterborne diseases, promoting clean environments, and fostering behavioral change through hygiene education. By integrating these three components, the program not only safeguards human health but also supports social and economic development, particularly in vulnerable communities where inadequate WASH services contribute to high morbidity and mortality rates. As a cornerstone of sustainable development, WASH plays a vital role in achieving universal health coverage and meeting international goals such as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 6: Clean Water and Sanitation. Summary on the Extent of Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) Program Table 2 revealed the consolidated summary on the extent of the water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) program in public elementary schools in Maa District, Division of Davao City. In general, it had a mean score of 4.20, interpreted as very extensive. This indicated that school administrators and teachers had prioritized the promotion of health and hygiene as part of the learning environment.

Table 2. Summary on the Extent of Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) Program

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Availability of Water Facility	4.21	Very Extensive
2	Availability of Handwashing Facility	4.24	Very Extensive
3	Availability of Toilet Facility	4.16	Extensive
Overall Mean		4.20	Very Extensive

The highest mean (4.24) is observed in the availability of handwashing facilities, which is rated Very Extensive, highlighting the schools’ commitment to ensuring learners can regularly practice proper hand hygiene. This result is supported by Nguyen et al., (2024), who emphasized that the provision of functional handwashing facilities with water and soap is crucial in reducing the spread of communicable diseases among schoolchildren. On the other hand, the lowest mean (4.16) pertains to the availability of toilet facilities, described as Extensive, suggesting that while sanitation facilities are present, some schools may still face issues related to cleanliness, accessibility, or water supply for flushing. This finding is consistent with Mwangi and Mutua (2024), who found that the sustainability of school sanitation facilities depends largely on consistent maintenance, adequate funding, and student engagement in

hygiene programs.

3.3. *Significant Relationship Between the Factors Associated with Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) and the WASH Program of Public Elementary Schools of Maa District, Division of Davao City*—The data presented in Table 3 illustrates the significant relationship between the factors associated with water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) and the implementation of the WASH program in public elementary schools of Maa District, Division of Davao City. The overall correlation coefficients r-value of 0.710 and a p-value of 0.000 reveal that the overall examined factors have significant positive relationships with the WASH program. This confirms a strong and statistically significant relationship between the identified WASH factors and the overall effectiveness of the WASH program. Hence rejecting the set null hypothesis.

Table 3. Significant Relationship Between the Factors Associated with WASH and the WASH Program of Public Elementary Schools, Maa District, Division of Davao City

Factors Associated with WASH	r	p-value	Decision on H ₀
Prevention and Control Practices	0.337	0.000	Reject
Sanitation and Hygiene	0.642	0.000	Reject
Evaluation and Consultation	0.425	0.000	Reject
Attitudes and Beliefs	0.607	0.000	Reject
Overall	0.710	0.000	Reject

Note. All correlations are significant at $p < .05$.

Among the factors, sanitation and hygiene recorded the highest correlation coefficient $r = 0.642$ and a p -value of 0.000, demonstrating a strong and significant influence on the WASH program. This finding highlights that effective sanitation practices and hygiene promotion are central in driving the success of WASH initiatives in schools. This suggests that prioritizing sanitation and hygiene education and facilities is vital to improving both health outcomes and program sustainability. Attitudes and beliefs also showed a strong correlation $r = 0.607$ and a p -value of 0.000, indicating that the values and perceptions of stakeholders are essential in supporting the WASH program. Positive attitudes and strong beliefs toward hygiene practices encourage compliance and create a culture of responsibility for maintaining clean and safe school environments. This finding underscores the importance of shaping mindsets and fostering collective commitment to achieve long-term behavioral change in WASH implementation. Evaluation and consultation yielded a moderate correlation $r = 0.425$ and a p -value of 0.000, signifying that monitoring, assessment, and stakeholder consultations contribute meaningfully to WASH program effectiveness. While not as strong as sanitation or attitudes, this factor highlights the role of feedback and continuous improvement in sustaining program outcomes. Regular evaluations ensure that practices are responsive to the schools' needs, while consultations strengthen collaboration among teachers, students, parents, and administrators. Lastly,

Relatively, the overall findings confirm that sanitation and hygiene, evaluation and consultation, and prevention and control practices are the most influential domains. This means that the set null hypothesis which no domains of the factors associated with WASH significantly influence water, sanitation, and hygiene program of public elementary schools of Maa District,

prevention and control practices revealed a moderate yet significant correlation ($r = 0.337$, $p = 0.000$), indicating that initiatives such as disease prevention campaigns, regular health monitoring, and hygiene education play a supportive but essential role in strengthening the overall effectiveness of the WASH program. While their influence is comparatively less pronounced than other factors like infrastructure availability, these practices remain crucial in sustaining a safe and healthy school environment, helping to prevent outbreaks, reinforce positive hygiene behaviors, and ensure the long-term success of school-based health interventions.

3.4. Regression Analysis on the Significant Influence of the Factors Associated with Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) on the WASH Program of Public Elementary Schools of Maa District, Division of Davao City—Table 4 presented the regression analysis on the significant influence of the factors associated with WASH on the WASH program in public elementary schools of Maa District, Division of Davao City. The regression analysis yielded an R -value of 0.716, indicating a strong correlation, while the R^2 value of 0.513 suggests that 51.3% of the variance in the WASH program can be explained by the four identified factors. The F -value of 30.235 with a p -value of 0.000 confirms that the analysis is statistically significant, validating the predictors as influential variables in shaping the implementation of the WASH program.

Division of Davao City, was rejected. Among the domains, sanitation and hygiene emerged as the strongest predictor of the WASH program with a standardized beta coefficient of 0.633 and a significant p -value of 0.036. This result highlights that sanitation facilities, clean water access, and the promotion of proper hygiene practices are central drivers of the WASH program's

Table 4. Regression Analysis on the Significant Influence of Factors Associated with WASH on the WASH Program of Public Elementary Schools, Maa District, Division of Davao City

Variables	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Decision on H ₀
Constant	-0.307	0.488	–	-0.630	0.530	–
Prevention and Control Practices	0.207	0.078	0.181	2.662	0.009	Reject
Sanitation and Hygiene	0.692	0.326	0.633	2.120	0.036	Reject
Evaluation and Consultation	0.289	0.078	0.252	3.697	0.000	Reject
Attitudes and Beliefs	-0.120	0.343	-0.103	-0.350	0.727	Failed to Reject

Note. $R = 0.716$, $R^2 = 0.513$, $F = 30.235$, $p < .05$.

effectiveness. It highlights the importance of prioritizing sanitation and hygiene-related interventions in schools to foster health and safety among learners and staff. Evaluation and consultation also showed a significant influence, with a standardized beta coefficient of 0.252 and a highly significant p-value of 0.000. This indicates that systematic monitoring, feedback, and collaborative consultations with stakeholders play a key role in sustaining the program. By regularly assessing progress and addressing gaps, schools ensure that WASH practices are aligned with community needs and remain responsive to emerging challenges. Prevention and control practices, with a standardized beta of 0.181 and a significant p-value of 0.009, were also found to contribute meaningfully to the

WASH program. This suggests that measures such as health campaigns, preventive education, and control of communicable diseases complement sanitation and evaluation efforts, making the program more comprehensive. While its effect is not as strong as sanitation and hygiene, its significance affirms that prevention strategies are vital for maintaining school health standards. In contrast, attitudes and beliefs, with a negative standardized beta coefficient (-0.103) and a non-significant p-value of 0.727, did not demonstrate a significant influence on the WASH program. This implies that while perceptions and values are important for compliance, they alone are insufficient in directly driving the success of the program compared to practical measures like sanitation, evaluation, and preventive practices.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This section gives the findings of the study based on the data outcome. The conclusions drawn from the findings of the study are also provided in this section. In order to make a significant contribution, the researcher has made recommendations in this chapter.

4.1. Findings—This non-experimental research using correlation design in this study aimed to determine the extent of factors associated with water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) and the extent of water, sanitation,

and hygiene (WASH) program of public elementary schools in Maa District, Division of Davao City. Specifically, this study aimed to determine the extent factors associated with water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) in terms

of prevention and control practices, sanitation and hygiene, and evaluation and consultation. Moreover, this acknowledged the extent of water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) program of elementary schools in terms of availability of water facility, availability of handwashing facility, and availability of toilet facility. Finally, this study determined the significant relationship between the extent factors of associated water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) and the extent of water, sanitation, hygiene (WASH) program of public elementary schools. Using non-experimental research, the extent of extent factors of associated water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) and the extent of water, sanitation, hygiene (WASH) program of public elementary schools was determined. The respondents of the study were the 92-public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City. A questionnaire based on the Three Star Approach for WASH in Schools: Field Guide developed by UNICEF and GIZ (2013) and DepEd Order No. 10, s. 2016, which outlines the policy and guidelines for comprehensive WASH implementation was utilized as the main instrument of this study. After thorough analysis, significant findings showed that the extent factors associated with water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) in terms of prevention and control practices, sanitation and hygiene, and evaluation and consultation was very extensive. In a similar way, the extent of water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) program of public elementary schools in Maa District in terms of availability of water facility, availability of handwashing facility, and availability of toilet facility was also very extensive which means that it was always manifested while in terms of factors associated with water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) which also very extensive. Overall, the composite correlation ($r = 0.710$, $p = 0.000$) indicates a highly significant and strong relationship between the combined WASH-related factors and the overall WASH program implementation.

This implies that the successful execution of the WASH program in public elementary schools in Maa District largely depends on the integration and enhancement of sanitation practices, attitudinal development, evaluation efforts, and preventive actions. The consistent rejection of the null hypothesis across all factors reinforces those improvements in these areas directly and positively affect the efficiency and sustainability of school-based WASH initiatives. Finally, indicators of factors associated with water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) such as prevention and control practices, sanitation and hygiene, and evaluation and consultation have significant influence on water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) program of public elementary schools of Maa District, Division of Davao City.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were offered: The factors associated with water, sanitation, and hygiene of public elementary schools was very extensive. The water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) program of public elementary schools was also very extensive. There was a strong positive relationship between factors associated with water, sanitation, and hygiene and WASH program of public elementary schools of Maa District, Division of City based on the indicators. Based on the revealed results, the indicators that strongly influence the factors associated with water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) on the overall implementation of the WASH program in public elementary schools are the availability of water facilities, availability of handwashing facilities, and availability of toilet facilities. These components collectively demonstrate that adequate infrastructure and access to essential hygiene facilities are vital in ensuring a safe, healthy, and learning-conducive school environment.

4.3. Recommendations—The following interventions were offered based on the conclusions of the study: Teachers should integrate WASH education into daily classroom routines

and activities to reinforce hygiene awareness and encourage lifelong healthy habits among learners. Learners may encourage to actively practice proper hygiene behaviors, such as regular handwashing and responsible toilet use, to maintain personal health and prevent the spread of diseases. Department of Education (DepEd) may allocate sufficient resources and implement stronger policies to sustain and expand the WASH program, particularly in underserved schools, ensuring equitable access to clean water and sanitation facilities. Future researchers should explore the long-term impact of WASH interventions on learners' academic performance and well-being to provide deeper insights that can guide evidence-based policy and program improvements.

5. References

- Abayneh Melaku, A., & Addis, T. (2023). Handwashing practices and associated factors among school children in kirkos and akaki kality sub-cities, addis ababa, ethiopia. *SAGE Open Medicine*, *11*, 11786302231156299. <https://doi.org/10.1177/11786302231156299>
- Adeola, F., & Yusuf, K. (2024). Evaluating the adequacy of school handwashing facilities and its influence on learners' hygiene practices in developing countries. *Journal of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development*, *14*(2), 201–213. <https://doi.org/10.2166/washdev.2024.037>
- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, *50*(2), 179–211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T)
- Al Saqri, S. H., Al Saidi, A. M., & Al Rawahi, A. Y. (2023). Assessing the implementation of wash programs in schools: A pathway to healthier learning environments. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, *20*(12), 6221. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20126221>
- Alipit, C. Y., Balane, M., Pestaño, Z., Lee-Llacer, A., Gervasio, R., Vasquez, C., Noubary, B., & Bacatan, E. (2025). Assessing the impact of handwashing nudges in urban public markets in the philippines during the covid-19 pandemic. *Journal of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development*. <https://doi.org/10.2166/washdev.2025.284>
- Aslam, M., Saleem, M., & Khan, N. (2023). Challenges and sustainability of wash facilities in public educational institutions. *Sustainability*, *15*(4), 2917. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15042917>
- Bansuan, S. A. (2023). Evaluation on the implementation of the comprehensive water, sanitation and hygiene in schools (wins) program of department of education in south central mindanao. *Psych Educ*, *7*, 78–95. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7644580>
- Becher, H., & Kowalski, L. (2024). Baseline assessment of handwashing behavior, hand hygiene conditions, and wellbeing in primary schools in nigeria. *International Journal of Public Health*, *70*, 1608656. <https://doi.org/10.3389/ijph.2025.1608656>
- Dalisay, S. N. M., Lumangaya, C. R., de Guzman, L. M. C., Leong, R. N. F., Siao, T. G., Leonardia, J. A., de Verya, C., & Belizario, V. Y. J. (2024). A qualitative analysis of the implementation of the water, sanitation, and hygiene in schools' program in the philippines using the one health lens. *International Journal of One Health*, *10*(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.14202/IJOH.2024.1-11>

- Dela Cruz, S. B., & Villanueva, J. M. (2023). Project safe: Development of handwashing process in cupang national high school for the improvement of wins evaluation. *Pinagpala Publishing Services*, 3(8). <https://www.pinagpalapublishing.com/publications/world-education-connect-multidisciplinary-e-publication/wec-2023-issues/vol-iii-issue-viii-august-2023>
- Dreibelbis, R., Greene, L. E., Freeman, M. C., Saboori, S., & Rheingans, R. D. (2013). The effect of a school-based handwashing promotion program on student absenteeism in rural bangladesh: A cluster-randomized trial. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 89(4), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.13-0140>
- EDCOM 2. (2025, January). 1,500 public schools don't have electricity; 1,000 without toilets. <https://www.rappler.com/philippines/last-mile-schools-no-electricity-toilets-poor-infrastructure-edcom-2-report/>
- Ene, N., Bolarinwa, O. A., & Adedigba, C. (2024). “if i use pad, i feel comfortable and safe”: A mixed-method analysis of knowledge, attitude, and practice of menstrual hygiene management among in-school adolescent girls in a nigerian city. *BMC Public Health*, 24, 1721. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-024-19256-5>
- for Development Studies (PIDS), P. I. (2024). Persistent diarrhea cases in ph highlight gaps in clean water access, pids study reveals. <https://www.pids.gov.ph/details/news/press-releases/persistent-diarrhea-cases-in-ph-highlights-gaps-in-clean-water-access-pids-study-reveals>
- Forro, R. D., & Besa, A. (2025). Water, sanitation, and hygiene in schools (wins) program, partners' commitment, and accomplishments of integrated schools in banga south cotabato. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 3(3). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15130941>
- Foundation, M. W. (2023). Manila water, manila water foundation complete handover of 72 refrigerated drinking fountains to qc public schools. <https://www.manilawater.com/corporate/agos/2023-12-15/manila-water--manila-water-foundation-complete-handover-of-72-refrigerated-drinking-fountains-to-qc-public-schools>
- Katembo, B. S., Hussein, H. I., Chandika, A. B., Masika, G. M., Njau, F. J., Nzagamba, B. L., & Kisangija, J. P. (2024). Practice and determinants of infection prevention and control measures among health care workers at benjamin mkapa hospital, dodoma-tanzania. *Health*, 16, 1027–1041. <https://doi.org/10.4236/health.2024.1611070>
- Khatun, N., Hossain, M., & Das, R. (2024). Challenges in sustaining school wash programs: The role of water storage and maintenance in rural education. *Environmental Health Insights*, 18(3), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1177/11786302241234567>
- Lacbay, R. A. (2024). Parental awareness on project water, sanitation and hygiene (wash) - wash in schools (wins) program. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 13(2), 11–17. <https://doi.org/10.5861/ijrse.2024.24801>
- Magsayo, L. (2024). The implementation of water, sanitations and hygiene (wins) program in city schools in division of davao city: An evaluation.
- Mananguit, A. J. C. (2024). The implementation of water, sanitation, hygiene in school (wins) program of public schools in the division of muntinlupa: A school-based management approach. *International Journal of Open-Access, Interdisciplinary & New Educational Discoveries*, 3(4). <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31670.10567>

- McLeroy, K. R., Bibeau, D., Steckler, A., & Glanz, K. (1988). An ecological perspective on health promotion programs. *Health Education Quarterly*, 15(4), 351–377. <https://doi.org/10.1177/109019818801500401>
- Mendez, V. A. (2024). Implementation of wash in schools (wins) program in baybay 2 district. *Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception Insights*, 2(1), 59–91. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13316785>
- Mwangi, J., & Awuor, P. (2024). Safe water access and hygiene practices in public schools: A framework for sustainable implementation. *Journal of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development*, 14(2), 276–288. <https://doi.org/10.2166/washdev.2024.056>
- Mwangi, P., & Mutua, J. (2024). Sustaining wash infrastructure in primary schools: Challenges and strategies in low-resource settings. *Journal of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development*, 14(1), 77–89. <https://doi.org/10.2166/washdev.2024.015>
- Nguyen, T. H., Le, M. T., & Tran, Q. A. (2024). School-based handwashing facilities and hygiene behavior: A confirmatory study of wash implementation effectiveness in southeast asia. *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health*, 252, 115178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2024.115178>
- of Children Philippines, S. (2021). Safe and equitable water, sanitation, and hygiene practices in schools and health facilities. <https://situationofchildren.org/safe-and-equitable-water-in-schools>
- of Education, D. (2016). Policy and guidelines for the comprehensive water, sanitation and hygiene in schools (wins) program (deped order no. 10, s. 2016). <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2016/02/19/do-10-s-2016-policy-and-guidelines-for-the-comprehensive-water-sanitation-and-hygiene-in-schools-wins-program>
- of Education, D. (2021). Deped wins report: More schools make great progress in water, sanitation, and hygiene conditions. <https://deped.gov.ph/2021/03/09/deped-wins-report-more-schools-make-great-progress-in-water-sanitation-and-hygiene-conditions/>
- Pereira, C. T., Sorlini, S., Sátiro, J., & Albuquerque, A. (2024). Water, sanitation, and hygiene (wash) in schools: A catalyst for upholding human rights to water and sanitation in anápolis, brazil. *Sustainability*, 16(13), 5361. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16135361>
- Philippines, U. (2022, October). Deped, doh, unicef, who and marikina city promote handwashing to create safe schools and communities. <https://www.unicef.org/philippines/press-releases/deped-doh-unicef-who-and-marikina-city-promote-handwashing-create-safe-schools-and>
- Philippines, U. (2023). Tawi-tawi schools need better water, hygiene and sanitation facilities. <https://www.unicef.org/philippines/stories/tawi-tawi-schools-need-better-water-hygiene-and-sanitation-facilities>
- Philippines, U. (2024, May). Tawi-tawi schools need better water, hygiene and sanitation facilities. <https://www.unicef.org/philippines/stories/tawi-tawi-schools-need-better-water-hygiene-and-sanitation-facilities>
- Poague, K. I., Blanford, J. I., Martínez, J. A., & Anthonj, C. (2022). School water, sanitation, and hygiene (wash) intervention to improve malnutrition, dehydration, health literacy, and handwashing: A cluster-randomised controlled trial in metro manila, philippines. *BMC Public Health*, 22, 14398. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-022-14398->

- Quinan, M. D. (2025). Wash in schools (wins): A mixed-methods assessment of program implementation in rural philippines. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 51(6), 1022–1033. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajess/2025/v51i62054>
- Rachmad, Y. E., Moka, A., Badriyyah, E. S. R., Gusliana, E., & Tawil, M. R. (2023). The effect of principal transformational leadership and motivation on performance of teacher in islamic elementary school. *Journal on Education*, 5(3), 7043–7056.
- Rahman, K., Ahmed, F., & Chowdhury, S. (2024). School sanitation practices and their impact on student health outcomes in south asia. *International Journal of Environmental Health Research*, 34(2), 220–232. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09603123.2024.1198476>
- Rivera, L. G. (2020). The implementation of water, sanitation and hygiene (wash) in schools (wins): An evaluation. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 9(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.5861/ijrse.2020.3486>
- Rosenstock, I. M. (1974). Historical origins of the health belief model. *Health Education Monographs*, 2(4), 328–335. <https://doi.org/10.1177/109019817400200403>
- Sangalang, S. O., Lemence, A. L. G., Ottong, Z. J., Valencia, J. C., Olaguera, M., Canja, R. J. F., Mariano, S. M. F., Prado, N. O., Ocaña, R. M. Z., Singson, P. A. A., Cumagun, M. L., Liao, J., Anglo, M. V. J. C., Borgemeister, C., & Kistemann, T. (2022). School water, sanitation, and hygiene (wash) intervention to improve malnutrition, dehydration, health literacy, and handwashing: A cluster-randomized controlled trial in metro manila, philippines. *BMC Public Health*, 22, 2034. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-022-14398-w>
- Singh, R., & Patel, N. (2024). Behavioral interventions to sustain school hand hygiene: The role of visual reminders and environmental cues. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 132(5), 54001. <https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP13254001>
- Sultana, R., Ahmed, T., & Karim, M. M. (2024). School-based water accessibility and hygiene management: Assessing the sustainability of wash facilities in primary education institutions. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 31(12), 15034–15047. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-024-31942-8>
- Tadesse, G., Alemu, M., & Workneh, D. (2024). School-based wash facilities and their influence on student attendance and hygiene behavior in developing contexts. *BMC Public Health*, 24(1), 1123. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-024-1123-7>
- Van der Velden, M. (2022). Improving toilet usability and cleanliness in public schools in the philippines using a packaged operation and maintenance intervention. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(16), 10059. <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/19/16/10059>
- Velasco, J. C. F., Perillo, F. T., & Largo, S. E. (2021). Wins proposal 2024. <https://www.scribd.com/document/700365404/wins-proposal-2024>
- Winter, J. C., Darmstadt, G. L., Lee, S. J., & Davis, J. (2021). The potential of school-based wash programming to support children as agents of change in rural zambian households. *BMC Public Health*, 21, 1812. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-11824-3>